

THE CULTURE OF INTERPERSONAL RELATIONSHIPS IN STUDENTS DEVELOPMENT NOW DAILY DOLLARITY

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Annotation: the article is about the current relevance and importance of the development of the culture of interpersonal relations in students, and more attention is paid to the importance of the formation of a culture of interpersonal relations between the student body oath say strengthening the personality of the greatest reforms until their implementation in our country, developing correct adequate decision-making in

Keywords: communication, culture of communication, attitude interpersonal relationships complex relationships culture of attitude decision decree.

Prosperous life – perfect from upbringing starts. It is known that young generation upbringing has always been important and relevant. But we In the 21st century, this issue has truly become a matter of life and death is going "Education how much perfect if people that's all happy lives" that sages who did not say it for nothing. Education should be perfect in the current volatile times "It is absolutely impossible to allow a gap to appear in this matter." dear President Shaukat Mirziyoyev 1 .

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Therefore, the consistent reforms carried out in our country, Uzbekistan Republic President Shaukat Mirziyoyev social and spiritual and educational to areas about young people in education new 7 important initiative, science, technique and rapid development of technologies, higher education institutions of foreign countries opening of branches and faculties, improvement of regulatory and legal support and material and technical conditions to improve directed country prospect for to educate young people who are able to take responsibility, enterprising, ambitious with one in line pedagogy higher education institutions future of teachers correcting their initiatives, eliminating conflict processes in them consistent with the educational system regarding the introduction and development of new literature changes is being entered. Uzbekistan Republic President 2017 year April 20 PQ-2909 - No. "On measures for further development of the higher education system" decision, 2017 year July 5 No. PF-5106 "To the youth about state policy efficiency Decree on increasing and supporting the activities of the Youth Union of Uzbekistan" and the Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated October 8, 2019 PF- No. 5847 "Development of the higher education system of the Republic of Uzbekistan until 2030 Decree on approval of the concept of developed countries of the world study of educational experiences, local conditions, economic and intellectual resources taking into account the implementation of fundamental reforms in all spheres of society the fact that it is being increased ensures the achievement of new achievements.

1. Uzbekistan Republic President Shaukat Mirziyoyev Uzbekistan young people of the union IV his speech at the congress, 2017.

also this to the activity about another regulatory and legal in the documents defined tasks in the implementation of this tutorial will serve to a certain extent. Independence years the roof in a sense Uzbekistan Republic socio-economic and cultural development defining the perspective, taking a worthy place among the countries of the world community is going on with the implementation of large-scale work on the path of aspiration. Uzbekistan Republic President Shaukat Mirziyoyev as noted: "High education system modern methods using efficient management, in the field material and technical base strengthen, educational method things improvement according to serious measures we need to see. Real economic sectors considered personnel customers determining the strategy for the development of the higher education system based on the needs, state education standards and qualification requirements again work exit, of students it is necessary to effectively organize qualification practice" 1 . This, in turn, is higher education intellectually, morally, spiritually strong, mature qualified staff of teachers to be requirement is enough.

Reform of the national education system, content of education, training of pedagogues and their qualification increase programs improvement and specialists by of textbooks new generation in creating is used.

Today, it is important to create a democratic model of education from issues is one. education, especially, education process democratic of the model initial

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element student of the person individual activity showing manifestation will be People between relationships according to problems psychological advice transfer in practice too much occurs and customer they This is when he complains about other problems of a personal nature, even if he doesn't talk about it directly in fact in it interpersonal relationships according to his problem that there is no does not mean In life while a lot cases of this the opposite to be output: if the client interpersonal relationships according to there is status if concerned so in case each always in it own it will be possible to determine the problem of personal content related to the character. In addition, the practical solutions to these two problems are similar in many respects is similar. Nevertheless, these problems should be considered separately because they are always somewhat different than a personal content problem solution will be done. That's it of a person another people with relationships manage the way with will be resolved. In contrast, a person always solves his personal problems individually and another people with directly contact without doing too solution reach possible

From this except personal and interpersonal content problems solution reach in methods big difference there is. if personal problems usually of a person internal interpersonal problems, if it is related to the need to fundamentally change their world a person's behavior is mainly related to the need to change the external forms. Psychological problems related to a person's interactions with others can be different in terms of features. They are personal with the people around them and practical mutual relations with depends being to him near and much long was for example, it applies to relations with relatives and strangers possible This problem obvious expressed young difference too have will be.

For example, of the client peers or another generation, much young yes from himself much can occur in interactions with older people. Interpersonal relationships problems different sexual to people too concerned to be possible

Saying passed of problems a lot dimensionality people between mutual of relationships complexity shows. This of problems most of them this on the ground we separately discussion if we do both however this problems in life to each other dependence and the majority cases complex solution to be done necessity from memory not to issue need For example, common difficulties arise in interpersonal relationships there are some common reasons for its occurrence. However, human relations are different types special was private, to himself special difficulties reasons too there is.

Interpersonal culture in students is the teacher's students with the psychological that is most convenient for him in class and extracurricular activities environment to the body causing positive spiritual the climate to create for chance giver professional is a relationship.

Teacher's students with mutually near communication main plan:

- negative circumstances to the body bringer all to processes I'm done to give
- in students independent thought conduct skills harvest to do;
- students to activity, free to think own opinions without fear statement by doing to him to rely on to teach;
- development of hidden abilities of students;

- lesson and from class except in processes joy and happiness get in the mood to do

Education receiver education - educational activity students with together organize is enough. In this of the class active students and informal leaders with mutually of communication fair to be important important has: students education different elements conscious to engage in independent performance, in which students are organized and executed roles to perform chance by creating to give must

Properly organized communication of the learner is the realization of the identity of the student function improves. In this education of the recipient task communication based on to help students to realize that they are "I", to express their opinion boldly and freely as a person to speak in the team own place to know self assessment to teach need

In students interpersonal relationship culture editorial communication structure in terms of is a unique example of student creativity. Pedagogical scientists of the learner students with communication many descriptions scientific in his works statement if they do communication, first education of the recipient personal psychological feature as manifestation will be

Students with corrective and developmental affairs

Education education in institutions educational of work the most important of duties one is the formation and development of the student body. It's not just this or that education applies not only to the educational institution, but also to a specific educational group - a class. Because where which in the team interpersonal relationships good organize done if there is, this team is the basis for successfully

fulfilling the social tasks in front of it will be created. It is also good to introduce self-management in such a team effects to give possible Interpersonal relationships learning methods one The sociometer is a hypocrite method. The concept of sociometry by the American scientist J. Moreno offer done being in the group mutual relationships learning said the meaning means Sociometric method interpersonal relations in different groups, communities features of learning in psychology wide applied the most efficient is one of the tools. Sociometric analysis of the data held by the individual in the group instead of in the group interpersonal of relationships features, group stars, group the leader (recognized leader of the group) is isolated from the group remaining) member of in the group small groups (micro groups), their content, mutually relations and again series that's it such as information get enable gives

When solving problems in the system of interpersonal relations with students training training take to go efficient the result will give. In this on the shore from exercises use can:

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